

Modelling the Energy Sector Based on Ghana's Energy Transition Policies

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Executive Summary

This study examined the future trajectory of Ghana's energy sector using the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) tool, focusing on three distinct scenarios: Business as Usual (BaU), the Energy Transition Framework (ETF), and the Energy Transition and Investment Plan (ETIP). The analysis evaluated the potential outcomes of installed capacity, power generation, total costs, and CO₂ emissions by 2070.

The BaU scenario projects a continued dominance of thermal power generation, leading to relatively lower costs and increased fossil fuel dependency, significantly increasing CO₂ emissions. In contrast, the Energy Transition Framework scenario envisions a more diversified energy mix, with a notable increase in renewable energy and improved energy efficiency, resulting in higher costs and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. The most transformative outcomes are observed in the Energy Transition and Investment Plan scenario, which emphasises large-scale investments in renewable energy, grid infrastructure, and energy storage. This scenario leads to net-zero CO₂ emissions in line with Ghana's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and other international climate obligations like the Paris Agreement.

The study highlights the critical importance of strategic policy interventions and targeted investments in achieving Ghana's sustainable, resilient, and economically viable energy sector. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, investors, and stakeholders, offering a robust evidence base for guiding the country's energy transition.

1. Introduction

Ghana has seen significant progress in its energy sector over the past few decades. However, with a population exceeding 31 million and a rapidly growing economy, the energy demand has surged, necessitating the expansion and modernisation of the power sector (GSS, 2022). This surge in demand has highlighted both the potential and the challenges within Ghana's power sector, necessitating a strategic and well-planned approach to ensure sustainable and reliable electricity supply for the future.

Between 2000 and 2022, electricity generation capacity, excluding distributed generation, increased by 5.5%, reaching 5,639 MW in 2023 (Energy Commission, 2023). This comprises hydro, thermal, and other renewable sources. As of 2023, hydro plants contributed 28.1% of the total installed capacity, with thermal plants and renewable sources contributing 69.6% and 2.3%, respectively (Energy Commission, 2023, 2024).

The large share of thermal plants, primarily fueled by natural gas, has played a critical role in stabilising electricity supply, but it has also introduced challenges related to fuel supply security and environmental sustainability in terms of high greenhouse gas emissions. As a country rich in natural resources such as hydro, solar, and wind energy, Ghana has the potential to achieve a sustainable and resilient electricity supply (GRIDCo, 2022). However, the path towards this goal is fraught with challenges, including infrastructure deficits, financial constraints, and the need for comprehensive policy frameworks to guide the energy transition.

The government of Ghana has recognised the need for a strategic approach to managing the energy sector. It has introduced several policy initiatives to transition to a more sustainable and resilient energy sector. Two key policy documents are the "Energy Transition Framework" and the "Energy Transition and Investment Plan" (Ministry of Energy, 2022; SEforALL, 2023). These documents outline the vision for the sector's transformation, emphasising the importance of renewable energy, energy efficiency, and targeted investments in infrastructure.

This study aims to model Ghana's energy sector using the OSeMOSYS energy modelling tool, focusing on the Business as Usual (BaU) scenario, the Electricity Transition Framework (ETF) scenario, and the Energy Transition and Investment Plan (ETIP) scenario. By comparing these scenarios, the study seeks to provide insights into the potential trajectories of the sector to inform policy decisions that will shape Ghana's energy future.

2. Methodology

The OSeMOSYS energy modelling tool was used to simulate the three scenarios for the study. OSeMOSYS is an open-source, optimization-based energy modelling tool that analyses complex energy systems over a long-term horizon, unlike other energy

modelling tools (Howells *et al.*, 2011). clicSAND, a novel user interface designed for OSeMOSYS that reduces the learning curve, was used for the modelling (Cannone *et al.*, 2024). The model was calibrated using historical data from the utilities and the starter data kit of Ghana's energy sector, including energy demand, generation capacity, fuel prices, and other relevant parameters.

As illustrated in Figure 1, three scenarios were considered;

1. **Business as Usual (BaU) Scenario**

The BaU scenario represents the continuation of current trends in Ghana's energy sector without significant policy changes or interventions. This scenario assumes existing policies and strategies remain in place, with no significant shifts in the energy mix, regulatory framework, or investment patterns. The BaU scenario provides a baseline against which the impacts of the other scenarios can be compared.

2. **Energy Transition Framework Scenario (ETF)**

The Energy Transition Framework scenario is based on the strategic guidelines outlined in Ghana's "Energy Transition Framework" policy document. This scenario envisions a shift towards a more sustainable and resilient energy sector, emphasising renewable energy, energy efficiency, and grid modernisation. Key components of this scenario include the accelerated deployment of renewables up to 20% of the energy generation mix, predominantly solar and hydro, the introduction of nuclear power in the mid-2050s, the adoption of energy efficiency measures across the value chain, and the strengthening of the transmission and distribution infrastructure to enhance grid reliability and resilience.

3. **Energy Transition and Investment Plan Scenario (ETIP)**

The ETIP scenario incorporates targeted investments and strategic planning to accelerate the transition to full decarbonisation. This scenario reflects the vision outlined in the "Energy Transition and Investment Plan," which focuses on mobilising financial resources, attracting private sector participation, and prioritising investments in key areas such as renewable energy, grid infrastructure, and energy storage. In this scenario, the study assesses the potential outcomes of full decarbonisation in the energy sector, introducing 10% nuclear power amidst renewables, particularly in grid expansion, and developing innovative technologies such as energy storage systems. It should be noted that an additional restriction was applied, linearly lowering the activity of the CO₂-emitting power plants from 2030 onwards.

Figure 1: Summary of modelling scenarios

For each scenario, the model simulated the evolution of the energy system through to 2070, in line with the transition plans. The model outputs include installed electricity capacity and supply projections, the energy mix, greenhouse gas emissions, and the costs associated with different energy pathways. The results were analysed to identify the key drivers of change in the energy sector and to assess the trade-offs between different policy options.

3. Results

3.1. Model Output

3.1.1. Installed Capacity

The installed capacity chart in Figure 2 provides a detailed overview of the projected expansion of Ghana's energy generation infrastructure across the three scenarios: BAU, ETF, and ETIP. These results highlight the anticipated changes in the composition of the energy mix, showing the relative contributions of thermal (single-cycle gas turbine, SCGT, and combined-cycle gas turbine, CCGT), hydropower, and renewable energy sources (solar, hydro, biomass) over time. By analysing this chart, we can understand the scale and pace of infrastructure development needed to meet future energy demand.

Figure 2: Annual installed electricity generation capacities (2022 - 2070)

In the BaU, hydropower is expected to grow from 1580 MW in 2022 to 2420 in 2030 MW after the maximum resource potential has been utilised, and its share remains relatively constant from 2030 to 2070. Notably, the installed capacity for the ETIP scenario is significantly higher than the other scenarios due to the increased penetration of solar energy. Solar energy has a capacity factor of about 24.5%, which is half of the natural gas (56.8%) in the BaU scenario, with the advantage of electrifying end-use sectors, thereby increasing electricity access.

3.1.2. Power Generation

As illustrated in Figure 3, power generation represents the electricity output from various energy sources in each scenario. It showcases the projected energy generation levels and the shifts in reliance on different technologies over the modelling period (2022 to 2070). The power generation forecast is critical for understanding how the evolving energy mix translates into electricity production and the implications for meeting Ghana's growing energy demand.

Figure 3: Annual power generation (2022 – 2070)

In the BAU scenario, Ghana's electricity generation continues to be dominated by thermal power plants, primarily fuelled by natural gas. For ETF, by 2070, renewables, particularly solar and hydro, account for 20% of the total generation capacity. Hydropower maintains a fairly stable generation, while the reliance on thermal power plants is reduced to make way for nuclear power. This diversification results in a more balanced and sustainable energy mix. The ETIP scenario represents the most aggressive shift towards renewable energy. By 2070, renewables, predominantly solar and hydro contribute 86% of the total generation capacity. Hydropower remains steady, while the share of thermal power is further reduced to 0%, replaced by about 10% nuclear power. This scenario envisions a significant expansion in energy storage systems to support the variability of renewable generation.

3.1.3. Total Cost

The total cost, as presented in Figure 4, is the comparative analysis of the overall financial implications of each scenario, including capital expenditures, operational and maintenance costs, and fuel expenses. This cost implication is essential for evaluating each pathway's economic viability and affordability, highlighting the long-term cost implications of different energy policies and investment strategies.

Figure 4: Annual total cost for each scenario

The BaU scenario reveals costs associated with fuel imports, particularly for natural gas. The total cost is estimated at around \$340 billion, driven by rising fuel costs and the need for frequent maintenance of ageing thermal plants. The transition to a more renewable-centric energy mix increases the total cost, estimated at around \$400 billion and \$500 billion by 2070, for ETF and ETIP scenarios, respectively. Although the initial capital costs for renewable energy infrastructure are high, the long-term operational savings and reduced fuel import costs contribute to a more sustainable economic model.

3.2. Emissions

CO₂ provides insights into the environmental impact of each scenario, focusing on the projected greenhouse gas emissions from the power sector. By comparing the emissions levels across the BaU, ETF, and ETIP scenarios, as shown in Figure 5, the results help assess the effectiveness of different energy strategies in mitigating climate change and contributing to Ghana's carbon reduction targets.

Figure 5: Total CO₂ emissions for different scenarios (2022 – 2070)

The BAU scenario results in a steady increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with total CO₂ emissions from the power sector projected to rise from approximately 13 MtCO₂ in 2022 to over 80 MtCO₂ by 2070. The heavy reliance on fossil fuels, combined with limited growth in renewables, exacerbates the environmental footprint of the power sector, leading to higher per capita emissions. The ETF scenario significantly mitigates GHG emissions compared to the BAU scenario. By 2070, total CO₂ emissions are projected to be around 37 MtCO₂, a 55% reduction compared to the BAU scenario. This reduction is primarily due to the increased penetration of renewables, the introduction of nuclear energy, and the improved efficiency of thermal plants by adopting more CCGTs. ETIP is a full net-zero scenario with GHG emissions forecasted to zero by 2070. The aggressive deployment of renewables, coupled with investments in energy efficiency and storage, results in a decoupling of electricity generation from carbon emissions, aligning with Ghana's commitments under international climate agreements.

4. Discussion

The results of the BaU scenario indicate that continuing on the current trajectory without significant policy changes will lead to a more carbon-intensive and costly energy sector. The heavy reliance on thermal power plants exacerbates Ghana's vulnerability to fuel price volatility and supply disruptions, which could undermine energy security. Moreover, the projected rise in GHG emissions under this scenario is inconsistent with global and national climate goals, suggesting that maintaining the status quo is unsustainable in the long term.

The Energy Transition Framework scenario demonstrates the potential benefits of a moderate policy shift towards renewables and energy efficiency. The results suggest that even with a balanced approach, significant environmental benefits can be achieved, including a substantial reduction in GHG emissions. Economically, this scenario offers a more stable and sustainable model, with lower fuel import costs and increased energy security. However, the pace of change might be insufficient to fully meet Ghana's long-term energy needs, particularly if demand growth outpaces renewable capacity expansion.

The Energy Transition and Investment Plan scenario represents the most ambitious and forward-looking approach, offering a pathway to a net-zero carbon emission and economically sustainable energy future. The significant reduction in GHG emissions aligns with Ghana's climate commitments, and expanding renewables and energy storage enhances energy security and resilience. This scenario, however, requires strong political will, robust policy frameworks, and international financial support to be realised fully.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implication

The comparative analysis of the three scenarios highlights the critical importance of policy intervention in shaping the future of Ghana's energy sector. While the BaU scenario underscores the risks of inaction, the Energy Transition Framework and Energy Transition and Investment Plan scenarios illustrate the potential benefits of a proactive approach to energy policy.

The study reveals that scenarios emphasizing renewable energy integration, particularly the ETIP, result in the most significant benefits in terms of cost reduction, emissions control, and energy security. To realize these benefits, policymakers should prioritize the development and implementation of policies that encourage investment in renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and biomass. Furthermore, the transition towards a more renewable-centric energy mix necessitates substantial upgrades and modernising the grid to handle the intermittency associated with variable energy sources. Therefore, Policymakers should focus on grid resilience by investing in smart grid technologies, energy storage systems, and improved transmission and distribution networks. Finally, there is the need for a consistent and transparent policy environment, essentially to attract the necessary investments for the energy transition. The ETIP scenario aligns closely with Ghana's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), as well as other international climate obligations like the Paris Agreement.

While the modelling results align with the envisioned trajectories from the three scenarios, the modelling assumptions could affect the accuracy of projections. It excludes external factors, such as global economic shifts and regional energy integration. Finally, uncertainties in policy implementation, technology adoption rates, and incomplete analysis of environmental and social impacts present challenges.

The results suggest that with the right policies and investments, Ghana can transition to a more sustainable, resilient, and economically viable energy sector, aligning with national development goals and global climate commitments.

References

- Cannone, C., Allington, L., de Wet, N., Shivakumar, A., Goyns, P., Valderrama, C., Kell, A., *et al.* (2024), “clicSAND for OSeMOSYS: A User-Friendly Interface Using Open-Source Optimisation Software for Energy System Modelling Analysis”, *Energies*, Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, Vol. 17 No. 16, p. 3923, doi: 10.3390/en17163923.
- Energy Commission. (2023), “2023 National Energy Statistics Bulletin”, available at: <https://www.energycom.gov.gh/newsite/index.php/planning/energy-statistics?download=420:2023-energy-statistics>.
- Energy Commission. (2024), “2024 National Energy Statistics Bulletin”, available at: <https://www.energycom.gov.gh/newsite/index.php/planning/energy-statistics?download=641:2024-energy-statistics>.
- GRIDCo. (2022), “2022 Energy Supply Plan”, available at: <https://gridcogh.com/elec-supply-plans/#1b57f868c5081f421>.
- GSS, G.S.S. (2022), “2021 Population and Housing Census”, available at: <https://census2021.statsghana.gov.gh/>.
- Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, S., Hughes, A., *et al.* (2011), “OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System: An introduction to its ethos, structure and development”, *Energy Policy*, Vol. 39 No. 10, pp. 5850–5870, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033.
- Ministry of Energy. (2022), “National Energy Transition Framework”, available at: https://www.energymin.gov.gh/sites/default/files/2023-09/FINAL%20GHANA%27S%20NATIONAL%20ENERGY%20TRANSITION%20FRAMEWORK_2023_compressed%20%281%29_compressed%20%282%29.pdf.
- SEforALL. (2023), “Ghana Energy Transition and Investment Plan”, available at: <https://www.seforall.org/our-work/initiatives-projects/energy-transition-plans/ghana>.

